

KEY INDICATORS

With 495,568 hectares, Sweden had 16.5% of its farmland under organic management, well above that of the EU (11.1%). From 2001-2024, the area almost trebled and growth was thus lower than in other EU countries. In 2024, organic products made up 6.7% of total food sales in Sweden, amounting to 2,006 million euros.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)	202,827 ha (6.6%)	495,568 ha (16.5%)
Area Growth from 2001 to 2024	144.3%	

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)	167,546 ha (10.3%)	372,835 ha (14.7%)
Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)	282 ha (3.8%)	713 ha (20.5%)
Grassland* (Share of Total)	35,000 ha (7.6%)	122,021 ha (26.3%)
Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)	N/D	N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)	3,589 (4.4%)	3,995 (6.8%)
Aquaculture Producers	N/D	N/D
Processors	540	870
Importers	121	336

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)	225 M €	2,006 M€ (6.7%)
Per Capita Consumption	25.3 €	190 €
Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024	791.6%	
Imports	N/D	120,544 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN SWEDEN

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on Eurostat, Jordbruksverket and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN SWEDEN

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on various sources including Statistics Sweden, Ekoweb, Ekologiska Lantbrukarna

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Sweden CAP strategic plan provides for a 23% increase in supported organic area, with a significant proportion of certified organic land, mainly grassland, not receiving support directly for being organic, but still eligible for other agri-environmental support. The planned expenditure on organic farming is set to fall by 2027 compared with 2018, with a decrease of 21% in the average payment per ha supported, despite a slight increase in payment rates per ha for different land uses. The decrease in the planned average support rate is assumed to be a result of a different balance between horticultural and other crops planned. There is no additional support for conversion compared with maintenance payments. As a result of the falling organic areas in Sweden, payment rates were increased in 2025 to the maximum P1 levels programmed.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	355 kha	437 kha (+23%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	11.8%	14.5% (+23%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	58%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	75 M€	73 M€ (-3%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	211 €	167 € (-21%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1)*	351 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	680 M€	23.1%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	840 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	6,020 M€	5.8%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	LIVESTOCK*
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2023	P1	0	147	492	737	177
	2025	P1	0	162	541	811	195
Change from 2023 to 2025			0%	10%	10%	10%	10%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2023	P1	0	147	492	737	177
	2025	P1	0	162	541	811	195
Change from 2023 to 2025			0%	10%	10%	10%	10%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2023	P1	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2025	P1	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

*Livestock rate based on 1 ha arable land per LU

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Sweden has had multiple organic action plans dating back to 1996. At 30%, Sweden has one of the highest share of land area targets in the EU, starting from a strong base. The 2021 certified organic area share (20.2 %) and the market share (8.9%) exceeded the previous action plan targets. It also has ambitious targets for organic share of public procurement. A significant focus of the plans is on training and information initiatives at all levels, including for staff and others engaged in public procurement and catering. Following a change in government policy, the current plan and the targets were suspended in 2024, which also saw a 10% reduction in certified organic land area.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2011-13	20% of UAA by 2013	6% of market by 2013 / 25% of public procurement
Current Action Plan	2018-30	30% of UAA by 2030	60% of public procurement

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2011 - 2013)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2018 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Sweden is negligible. Sweden was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. As the funding, if any, is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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